

The Impact of Destination Image for Creative-Hub Business: Case Study of Bumi Arsa Creative Space

Rahanandra Hadyan Anshari¹, Nila Armelia Windasari²

^{1,2}School of Business and Management, Institut Teknologi Bandung

ABSTRACT: Over time, the growth of tourist destinations has led to a lot of new kinds of places to visit. One of them is making a "creative hub," which is a place where creative people can meet and work together. On the other hand, the tourism industry's incredible growth over the past fifty years has made it hard to market tourism. So, tourism marketers must now try to influence customer decisions in a global industry that is getting more complicated and competitive. A place needs to be in a good place in the minds of consumers for advertising to work in the targeted markets. Based on how destination image and creative hub are related, Bumi Arsa is one of the brands or businesses that are part of the creative hub industry. The problem with creative hub tourism is that they have to prove themselves to the market. According to the Bumi Arsa research respondent, they either didn't know yet or even misinterpreted about the creative hub business model that leads into lack of unique selling point awareness (Bumi Arsa, 2022). The purpose of this research is to comprehend the perceived destination image and determine the expected destination image of Bumi Arsa. Therefore, this is qualitative research using descriptive methods analysis based on the destination image form framework as the baseline. The analysis used in this study uses internal and external point of view analysis with situation analysis (5C) to map current Bumi Arsa marketing performance, root cause analysis by fishbone diagram to determine the root cause of the business issue, Model of the formation of destination image as the basis of the research design, and destination image attribute to elaborate each factor that will affect the destination image for a creative hub. The findings of this thesis explain that in order to decide the expected destination image for a creative hub using the destination image form framework, a destination needs to manage expectations between the market perspective and internal business team based on the destination image attribute.

KEYWORDS: Bumi Arsa, Creative Hub, Destination Image Form Framework, Tourism Marketing

INTRODUCTION

On a local and global scale, creative economies generate economic as well as social benefits for cultures and communities. The creative economy, according to a UNCTAD report (2010), has the ability to generate revenue and jobs while also fostering social inclusion, cultural variety, and human development. The Creative Hubs Report (2016) characterizes 'hubs' as a way of organizing work that has evolved in different sectors and various organizations in the last 10 years. Creative hubs hold the possibility of strengthening the cultural and creative industries by bringing together a local community of professionals, supporting its valorization, cultivating a sense of ownership, or improving working conditions (Hub Barometer, 2017).

The tourism industry's phenomenal growth over the previous fifty years has produced significant obstacles in tourism marketing. As a result, tourism marketers must now influence customer decisions in an increasingly complex and competitive global industry. The necessity for an effective destination positioning plan is one of the most significant marketing issues resulting from this predicament. The significance of destination image in understanding travel behavior and devising effective tourism marketing strategies highlights the need for approaches to completely and accurately measure this concept.

Sukabumi City, one of the tourist destinations in the province of West Java, has sufficient natural and cultural potential to be developed as a tourist attraction. On the other hand, there are several challenges faced with the creative hub business model type in Sukabumi. based on the author's observations & short questionnaire with local Sukabumi market, there are two depictions of major issues pertaining to the tourism industry in Sukabumi City in general and creative space in particular:

Figure 1. Leisure & Tour Options for Sukabumi Market Chart

Residents of Sukabumi who are unfamiliar with creative space and for whom creative space is still a novel concept. Only 10% are already familiar with creative space concepts as their leisure & tour destination.

Figure 2. Sukabumi Market Leisure Destination Preference

Residents of Sukabumi continue to visit first-tier cities such as Bandung, Jakarta, and Bogor on weekends for tourism and lifestyle reasons. From the figure 1.5, the author gets the prominent result that 80% of the sample choose to go outside the city to the nearest big city around Sukabumi itself. The author tried to elaborate the root cause using the RCA model by fishbone diagram approach.

Figure 3. Fishbone Diagram of the Bumi Arsa

From the RCA or fishbone diagram before, the author concluded that there is a misinterpretation of the business model of Bumi Arsa in the point of view of the consumers or Sukabumi market specifically. The biggest homework of Bumi Arsa and the author is to drive and build the right destination image perception to the target market and offer the most fit and suitable brand communication strategy to build a brand trust into the market, also to develop some of the business schemes to create an exceptional attraction to the market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Root Cause Analysis

Root Cause Analysis (RCA) is a structured approach to identify influencing factors on a business issue so that it can be used to improve performance (Corcoran, 2004). In addition, the use of RCA in performance improvement analysis according to Latino and Kenneth (2006) can facilitate tracking of the factors that affect performance. Root Cause is part of several factors (problems, conditions, organizational factors) that becomes a possible cause and is followed by an undesirable effect expected.

Fishbone Diagram

Fishbone Diagram or Ishikawa Diagram is a root cause analysis technique that shows several causes of a particular problem or event. Specifically, the Fishbone Diagram is shaped like a fish skeleton, this diagram is commonly used for cause and effect analysis to identify complex causal interactions of a particular problem or event. Fishbone diagrams can be a comprehensive theoretical framework to represent and analyze root causes (Coccia, 2018).

Destination Image Definition & Formation Process

In the context of tourism, destination image can be characterized as a continuous mental process in which one retains a set of impressions, emotional thoughts, beliefs, and prejudices about a location as a result of information collected from various sources (Crompton, 1979; Liou, 2010; Milman, 2011; Reynolds, 1965). In the world of tourism, destination marketing literature has coincided with the effect of image on a place's overall success (Chen and Kerstetter, 1999; Crompton, 1979; Hanlan and Kelly, 2004; Hunt, 1975). On another perspective, destination image is the expression of an individual's or group's objective knowledge, prejudices, imagination, and emotional feelings about a certain site (Lauson and Bovy, 1977). As a result, destination image plays a major role in the many travel decision-making models that have been created to date (Schmoll, 1977; Moutinho, 1984; Woodside And Lysonski, 1989).

Figure 4. Model of the Formation of Destination Image

The author attempts to separate figure 2.2 into two variables that influence the construction of the target image. Information sources, also known as stimulus factors (Baloglu and McCleary 1999a) or image producing agents, are forces that influence the formation of perceptions and assessments (Gartner, 1993).

Brand Communication and Brand Trust

Communication is the human activity that connects individuals and builds relationships. Communication activities such as meaning creating and organizing play a significant part in the development of brand relationships (Duncan and Moriarty, 1998). Brand communication is the major integrative factor in managing brand connections with customers and generates good brand attitudes such as brand satisfaction and brand trust (Kempf and Smith, 1998). Brand communication is meant to drive consumer trust and perception of the brand. The concept of brand trust in the branding literature is founded on the concept of a brand-consumer relationship, which is viewed as a substitute for personal contact between the company and its consumers (Sheth and Parvatiyar, 1995; Zehir et al.2011).

Trust in the purchased brand may be considered as an leveraging of its credibility, which may support consumers' repeat purchasing behavior. The domain of trust in this study is a desirable benefit in relational exchanges (Agustin and Singh, 2005; Sahin et al.2011). The concept of brand trust is related to brand communication and consumer satisfaction with a certain brand in a product class and is gaining prominence in consumer behavior. The importance of customer trust in the brand cannot be overstated.

Conceptual Framework

As the objective of this paper is to build a fit destination image that suits Bumi Arsa target market, the author set 3 stages of building a destination image for Bumi Arsa. There are formation images, Development Image of the business, and destination image output. These stages are from the user journey as their natural flow of user decision process to determine their leisure destination.

Figure 5. Conceptual Framework of Bumi Arsa Destination Image

First is picture creation. In this stage, the author will determine the 2 main reasons people visit leisure destinations. The author divides the literature into informational and personal sources. Informational sources included how people or target consumers prefer to be touched or approached and what content and communication fits the business model and market. Personal aspects are also important. On this factor, the author will focus on target market expectations, motivations, preferences, and benchmarks for leisure destinations and activities. The author will also discuss our target market's socio-demographics.

Second stage of the business strategy to cover the shortfall from the previous stage. During the development stage, the company will concentrate on how it can meet the expectations of its target market regarding the destination dimension attribute and how it can create some attractions to fulfill the requirements of the market.

The last stage is destination image output, which will generate Bumi Arsa perceived destination image from the market perspective. This stage will be focusing on how Bumi Arsa could retain their number of visitors, brand awareness, and purchase level to meet the business needs.

METHODOLOGY

Data Collection

To author research objectives, the author will use both primary and secondary data collection. For the primary data itself, the author uses a qualitative research approach to gain a deep dive understanding of the business issue. Hence, there is a difference to get both types of data (primary and secondary data).

The author gathers primary data with a qualitative research approach that refers to a methodology for doing market research that centers on the collection of information via communication that is free-form and conversational in nature. The qualitative research technique is a method that is used to address research questions relating to data in narratives that originate from interviewing people, observing people, and researching documents. In this business case, the author will use the FGD method to gain understanding for Bumi Arsa market representative. This could lead to visibility from Bumi Arsa target market expectation and also from other stakeholders that are involved in the creative hub industry.

Table 1. Target Respondents of FGD Bumi Arsa

Candidate	Criteria	Qty
Bumi Arsa Target Market	- 18-35 Years old with SES B-C - Person who attached to the creative or community industry in West Java (Specifically around Sukabumi area)	6-10

In addition to focus group discussions (FGD), the author conducts in-depth interviews (IDI) for the purpose of this qualitative study. In contrast to the many other methods of qualitative research, the researchers who use an in-depth interviewing technique spend a considerable amount of time conversing with each participant. The purpose of this approach is to gain a deeper understanding on the performance of Bumi Arsa as a business and marketing perspective. On the IDI approach, the author will conduct one-on-one interviews with several stakeholders that are involved and also affected to the business from the internal side, and this IDI research to the internal stakeholders which is someone that is involved and has more experience and knowledge about the industry itself.

Table 2. Target Respondents of IDI Bumi Arsa

Candidate	Criteria	Qty
Internal Bumi Arsa Team	- Working as Bumi Arsa management team - Have a deep involvement in corporate strategic team, especially in the marketing area	1

The results of both the FGD and the IDI study will be analyzed in further depth for the conceptual framework (figure 5) presented in the prior chapter by the author. This analysis will focus on factors such as personal preference and informational sources.

RESEARCH DESIGN

To discuss more about how the author does the research, the author will describe the research design flow in the figure 6 below.

Figure 6. Research Design

Research design serves as a kind of road map for carrying out marketing research projects; they lay out the steps that must be taken to gather the data that will be used to create hypotheses and draw conclusions (Malhotra, 2007). Both exploratory and conclusive

research strategies exist. The objective of this study is to investigate something in order to learn more about it and have a better understanding on the issue. In this case, exploratory research is used to provide preliminary hypotheses or insights, guide any necessary follow-up studies, and pinpoint areas where further information is required. (Aaker et al, 2007; Malhotra, 2007).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

To simplify the elaboration of our research result, the author will try to examine each factor's understanding by elaborating what is the main focus understanding that will be discussed in the research result based on the destination image formation model to gain understanding about market expectation that will lead into the desirable destination image;

Table 3. Research Factors Focus

Factor	Sub Factors	Internal Bumi Arsa (Internal, IDI)	Target Market Perspective (External, FGD)
Informational Sources	Content Plan Preferences	Existing content deliverable	Type of engaging content
	Medium of Information	Existing channel used	Frequently used channel to gain information
	Trust of Sources	Engagement performance each channel	Medium with most impact with their decision
Personal Factors	Decision Flow	Drivers of existing visitors	User journey of the target market to visit destination
	Destination Requirement & Expectation	Bumi Arsa Business & services specification	Business & services specification for any occasion that build expectation
	Preferable Time & Occasion	Reason & motivation of existing visitors	Drivers and reason the target market would visit Bumi Arsa

Informational Sources Analysis

In the informational sources, the author aimed to gain understanding of how people could be exposed or search for information that triggered their need to visit some destinations. This section will elaborate on the 3 focus topics, content plan preferences, medium of information or communication, and trust of the sources.

Content Plan Preferences

This section focuses on discussing the content marketing strategy. By the definition, Content marketing is the process of developing and distributing relevant and useful content to existing customers and potential customers. One of the respondents said content with good and catchy quality with comprehensive information could unintentionally drive himself to digging more about the destination (Kurnia, 2022). Carrying on with the previous statement, the other respondents considering content with the type of video content are more likely to explain more about the destination or the business (Aruman, 2022). Both statements lead to the understanding that the quality of the content is equivalent with the informational context that is given to the exposed users and could drive their unconscious desire to know more about the business.

Continuing the context of how the market sees content as their drivers, the type of content that could be more engaging is the content who could simplify the information as short as possible and also give the hook or punchlines at the same time. This understanding was from the statement of one of the respondents that said that the more length of the content time tends to decrease their attention

and interest to receive the information from the content itself (Fadil, 2022). Besides the length of the content time, content with typical scene-cut models are more likely to deliver information more effectively to the users (Fadil, 2022).

From the content plan factor that affected the users consideration, the author gained an understanding that good quality of content deliverable is content that has video with scene-cut type with short length of the content time and also with catchy and comprehensive information given in the content deliverable.

Medium of Information

This section will be focusing on discussing the sources of people gaining the information, or the author will specifically discuss marketing channel strategy. A marketing channel strategy is a plan that outlines how a firm will connect with its clients via the many different marketing channels that are available.

From the target market perspective, one of our respondents said that each marketing channel currently has their own objectives and absolute different function and impact to their decision making (fadil, 2022). The respondents were also more likely to get exposed with the information from those (social media) channels since the usage of both channels were categorized as highly intense from their perspective.

According to one of our respondents, he is using instagram as a source of validation and gaining complete information of some brands before reaching the brand by personal chat (Fazariandi, 2022). In addition, the use of social media as informational sources gathering for those who are not yet visiting the place are the main channels to build expectation on customer mind (Kurnia, 2022). Therefore, the buildup of social media as a medium to deliver information about the place is very critical to make the right and suit market expectation as the business offers.

Social media could be the medium to dig more market interest, but there is another way to hook up the awareness of the market unintentionally. Advertising (online & offline) is one of the mediums to gain organic awareness from un-touch target market. One of the respondents said that social media or google ads could be so effective to trigger their action to explore more about the brand, in this case about the place (Aruman, 2022). So in this statement the author concludes that there is a connection between gaining market awareness by advertising with proper targeting and retaining their interest to keep searching more by social media medium.

Trust of The Sources

This factor will be focusing on how each source gives an impact to the market decision by relating their expectation with other people's validation. From the market perspective, there are several variables that could impact their trust into some brand or in this case into some destination place. One of the respondents said that he is more trustworthy with third parties' comments or recommendations to the place which leads to the reviews of the destination (Fadil, 2022). Building trust to the sources are very dependable to the eligibility of who gives the information to the market.

Medium or sources with more traffic (or in this case, followers & engagement rate) could give a positive impact to the users. Kurnia said that instagram or tiktok are his main medium to receive first impressions of the place, but he is also very considerate about how big the traffic that the medium has.

Other than that, social media collaboration leads to buildup market expectation of Bumi Arsa about the place from a specific related group or community, which could give a higher trust from the market

Brand Trust from Informational Sources Analysis

After the author gathered all the insight from internal and external stakeholders that affected the business, we tried to generate the overall flow of brand trust validation that could be built up from a market perspective.

Figure 7. Informational Process & Market Validation of Creative Hub (Brand Trust)

From figure 4.4, the author simplifies the process of how markets validate their information about destination image into 4 main checkpoints. These 4 steps are required to determine pre-visit expectation building from secondary information they received from any medium.

Personal Factors Analysis

The purpose of this section is to be able to better know the factors that affect the customer decision-making process on choosing to go to a destination. The author will try to elaborate by having two sides of perspective, from the internal Bumi Arsa business itself and from the external side of the market perspective point of view. This part will specifically elaborate three main topics, which are decision flow, destination requirement & expectation, and preferable time & occasion.

Decision Flow - User Journey

Consumers involve environments that influence their thoughts and perception which make it important to be aware of consumer behavior as a dynamic thing (Peter & Olson, 2010). In this section, the author aimed to comprehensively understand the end-to-end journey of a customer as a part of consumer behavior starting on what factors that influence them until they decide to go to a creative hub.

The first step on motivating the customer to start their decision making process is from getting informational sources. Most of the respondents said that they will receive the information regarding the destination first where it can be received through marketing advertisements from Bumi Arsa or from word of mouth of their colleagues. From this point of view, word of mouth (offline & online) is one of main drivers that influence customers on deciding to their next decision making journey.

After getting first-hand information regarding the destination, customers will try to do their personal research details to validate the information received with the actual services provided by the destination. will try to do his own research to check whether the information gathered from the previous step is valid and still as expected or not (Dio, 2022).

Before deciding the right time to go to a creative hub, he would invite his friends or group to go together to hangout and chill (Fazariandi, 2022). From this point, most customers will intend to go to a creative hub as a group and they aim to hangout. Finally, if customers find a group to go together with, they will search for the perfect time to go with their group.

Destination Requirement and Expectation

The purpose of this section aimed to be able to identify what facilities are expected from a market perspective, but they are currently not yet available at Bumi Arsa. Customer centricity is the ability to understand customers' situations, perceptions, and expectations to create customer satisfaction, loyalty and advocacy (Fader, 2020).

Most of our respondents basically expect the same basic facilities, which are food & beverage, indoor & outdoor, wifi connection, and public toilets. Besides live music, there is also one of our respondents that expects some art exhibitions or ongoing events when he thinks about a creative hub since if he only wants to eat, he basically can go to a coffee shop or eatery (Dika, 2022). From this point-of-view, ongoing art performances such as live music, exhibition, and events are expected by market perspective to add spice to their activity in a creative hub to build satisfaction since these kinds of activities come up in the customer top of mind when they hear the term "Creative" in creative hub.

One of our respondents also expects activity that they can do together with their group (Aisyah, 2022). This aligned with the previous statement from Kurnia (2022) that he would like to go in the form of a group instead of going alone. From this discussion, it can be seen that most of the customers expect that they can do a lot of group activities considering they intentionally come with their group.

Preferable Time & Occasion

This part will be focusing on identifying the last step in the customer decision making process which is how they choose the most preferable time and the right occasion to go to a creative hub. From the market perspective itself, Most of the respondents tend to go to a creative hub to attend a special occasion. Fadil (2022) already said that he would go to a creative hub with an objective to see or attend an ongoing event.

The decision-making is also influenced by the competitive advantage possessed by creative hubs where they provide a platform for holding art performances or events which other destinations do not always have. Fadil (2022) also stated that if he only wants to eat

and hangout with his friends, he can directly go to other coffee shops or eateries instead. Basically, customers will decide to go to a creative hub to do a special occasion which is mostly to attend an ongoing event or art performance.

One of the respondents said that he will definitely go to a creative hub during the weekend because he wants to spend the entire day on that destination (Wisnu, 2022). From this discussion, the author analyzed that besides customers will go based on an ongoing event that captivated them, they will also prefer to go to a creative hub with the condition as long as they have free time.

Expected Destination Image Attribute from Business Specification

After the author gained understanding and insight from both internal and external stakeholders involved in the making of destination image attribute, we tried to elaborate and explain more using destination image attribute factors which will have an output of expected destination image from market needs and also from Bumi Arsa business and brand offers.

Table 4. Desirable Destination Image Attribute Bumi Arsa

Market Expectation & Business Offer	Destination Image Attribute			
	Atmosphere of The Place	General Infrastructure	Tourist Infrastructure	Leisure & Recreation
Market Expectation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun • Enjoyable • Attractive site 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private & Public Transport (i.e: toilet & hangout places) • Telecommunications (i.e: wifi & internet connection) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food & Beverage Stalls • Ease of access to destination • Network of tourist information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entertainment (Art & Community) • Shopping • Group activities
Bumi Arsa Offers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun • Enjoyable • Good reputation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private & Public Transport (i.e: toilet & hangout places) • Telecommunications (i.e: wifi & internet connection) • Health Services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food & Beverage Stalls (tenant partner) • Ease of access to destination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entertainment (Creative & Community) • Shopping
Expected Destination Image	A one-stop creative space destination used to accommodate and appreciate your creative work. Reliable and trusted by 50+ creative collaborators	Reliable place to covers all of your needs as well as support the community & creative collaborators	Secure your tummy one call away with variety of tenants you can find on the creative hub	Chill and vibe together with variety of art performance & events in the one-stop creative space, Bumi Arsa

PROPOSED MARKETING STRATEGY

The author already conducts the research about market expectation for creative hubs as their destination. Therefore, to answer the research objective number which generates a desirable destination image and marketing communication plan to amplify Bumi Arsa awareness as the desirable destination image, the author will elaborate both of them in this section. Below is the desirable destination image of Bumi Arsa that will be the basis of our marketing strategy.

Figure 8. Bumi Arsa Desirable Destination Image Form

To make sure all of those 4 attributes could transfer and deliver effectively and have a right target, therefore the author will elaborate on the marketing and brand communication plan as the main strategy to build up and manage the destination image of Bumi Arsa. In this section, the author will divide the strategy into 3 sequence steps: build up trigger, knowledge deliverable medium, and visitor retaining & maintaining awareness plan.

Build Up Trigger

The build up trigger stage is focusing on how Bumi Arsa could reach their potential customers both from creative collaborators or even for the public to know and be aware of Bumi Arsa as a creative hub destination brand.

Table 5. Bumi Arsa Build Up Trigger Strategy

Type of Medium	Targeting Affinity or Spot	Channel Details	Call Action to	Key Visual & Conversion Plan
Online Channel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 18-35 Years Old around West Java - Creators & Creative Industry Person - Community & Event Enthusiast 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social Media Ads - Search Engine Optimization (SEO) 	Bumi Arsa Instagram	<p>Key Visual:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highlight of the Bumi Arsa venue as creative & hangout space - Cap-cut video highlight of event & activity in Bumi Arsa <p>Conversion Plan:</p> <p>All the medium will have call to action (CTA) button that redirect into Bumi Arsa social media account</p>
Offline Channel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Crowd spot at Sukabumi 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mini Billboard 	- Bumi Arsa Instagram	<p>Key Visual:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Upcoming Big Event in Bumi Arsa - Community Features in Bumi Arsa

	- Entrance way from outside Sukabumi	- T-banner along the side of the way	- Contact Center of Bumi Arsa	Conversion Plan: - KV Search Bar of Bumi Arsa Instagram on the Design and contact center
--	--------------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------------	---

Knowledge Deliverable Medium

The purpose of this step is to be able to provide the expected informational context of Bumi Arsa to the triggered customer on the previous step. By providing the right information needed by customers combined with their content preferences, Bumi Arsa is expected to have better engagement as well as maximize its content delivery as the main channel in terms of the information provider. Knowledge deliverable medium will be divided into two parts, which are Bumi Arsa website and social media.

The first channel is the Bumi Arsa website. Network of tourist information included as a part of the tourist infrastructure attribute that was expected by the market. By developing a channel-owned website, Bumi Arsa can provide an information channel for customers that are interested and still in the validating phase of their decision-making journey where they can find out all information regarding Bumi Arsa by searching Bumi Arsa on their browser. Based on our suggestion to fulfill the needs of information delivery, this information or section should be on the website.

- Home (Ongoing event countdown and what’s new on Bumi Arsa)
- About Us (Quick introduction about Bumi Arsa and Bumi Arsa’s Contact Person)
- Facilities (All the facilities for the customer and list of all tenants)
- Activity (Activity detailed calendar regarding the ongoing events)
- FAQ (Frequently Asked Question regarding Bumi Arsa)
- Chatbot (Simple chatbot that can connect the user to Bumi Arsa’s customer service)
- Creative Collaborators Registration Page

The second medium is Bumi Arsa Social Media. Instagram and Tiktok is one of the current main social media of Bumi Arsa for providing relevant information to the customer. To be able to improve the performance of Bumi Arsa’s social media content, Bumi Arsa needs to better understand its target market content and market preferences. From the FGD that has already been conducted, there are some gaps for improvements with the purpose of delivering the right and engaging content for Bumi Arsa target market.

First, Bumi Arsa can create a video-type post that shows the audience clearly about Bumi Arsa as a creative hub and what Bumi Arsa provides for their audience. In an effort to create more hooks for the audience, Bumi Arsa also can use locally preferred KOL as a guide that explains the content. The higher trustworthiness of a KOL will result in more effectiveness of KOL usage as well (Xiong, Cho, Law, et al, 2021). On creating the video-type content, Bumi Arsa also needs to watch out for the duration. Longer duration tends to make the audience get bored easily.

Second, instead of Bumi Arsa keeping providing information to their audience, Bumi Arsa also can create engaging content so Bumi Arsa is able to interact with their audience as well. This type of content aimed to boost Bumi Arsa’s account engagement with their audience and create closeness in the term between the information provider and the customer itself.

Visitor Retaining & Maintaining Awareness

The last stage of this marketing plan sequence is how we can retain the awareness and interest from current visitors to revisit Bumi Arsa and possibly expand the awareness to their relatives. On this stage, Bumi Arsa will collaborate with related communities or influencers to share their experience to their traffic or audience that aims to engage and widen the awareness of Bumi Arsa itself to the appropriate market. Selection of the communities and influencers that will be used for this stage really determines whether the retention and maintaining awareness of Bumi Arsa will work or not. The role of influencers is to recapture their followers or traffic to be informed about Bumi Arsa. Below are examples of influencers who have the impression of creative industry and traveling.

Figure 4.11. Targeted Creative & Event Influencers: Ernanda Putra

Figure 4.12. Targeted Creative & Event Influencers: Wishnutama

CONCLUSION

This paper intended to assist Bumi Arsa to figure out their destination image that matches with their target market preference. It is clear from the fishbone diagram that the primary root cause of the Bumi Arsa issue is a misinterpretation of the business model of Bumi Arsa in the point of view of the consumer's perception especially in the creative hub business itself. By utilizing analysis with situation analysis (5C) to map current Bumi Arsa marketing performance, RCA analysis by fishbone diagram to determine the root cause of the business issue, Model of the formation of destination image as the basis of the research design, and destination image attribute to elaborate each factor that will affect the destination image for a creative hub. As a result of this research, there are 3 marketing communication plans that will help Bumi Arsa to distribute their destination image to their target audience.

REFERENCES

1. Almeyda, M., & George, B. (2017). Place branding in tourism: a review of theoretical approaches and management practices. *Tourism & Management Studies*, 13(4), 10-19.
2. Anholt, S. (2007). Nation-brands and the value of provenance. In *Destination branding* (pp. 41-54). Routledge.
3. Anholt, S. (2009). *Handbook on tourism destinations branding*. World Tourism Organization (WTO).
4. Azhari, R., Wahyuni, S. K., & Saputra, R. A. (2017). Sukabumi Virtual Guide Tourism Berbasis Sistem Informasi Geografi. *Simnasiptek 2017*, 1(1), 96-100.
5. Benjamin, S., Dillette, A., & Alderman, D. H. (2020). "We can't return to normal": committing to tourism equity in the post-pandemic age. *Tourism Geographies*, 22(3), 476-483.
6. BPS 2021b. *Statistik Wisatawan Nusantara 2020*. Jakarta: Badan Pusat Statistik
7. BPS Kota Sukabumi (2021). *Kota Sukabumi dalam Angka 2020*. Kota Sukabumi: Badan Pusat Statistik
8. BPS. (2020). *Berita Statistik Kunjungan Wisatawan Semester 1 Selama Pandemi*. Jakarta: Badan Pusat Statistik
9. BPS. 2021a. *Statistik Kunjungan Wisatawan Mancanegara 2021*. Jakarta: Badan Pusat Statistik
10. Chan-Olmsted, S. M., & Shay, R. (2015). Media branding 3.0: From Media brands to branded entertainment and information. In *Handbook of media branding* (pp. 11-32). Springer, Cham.
11. Devison, R. A., Tyesta, L., & Herawati, R. (2017). Tugas Dan Fungsi Dinas Pemuda, Olahraga, Pariwisata Dan Ekonomi Kreatif Kota Sukabumi Dalam Pengelolaan Objek Wisata. *Diponegoro Law Journal*, 6(1), 1-16.
12. Fafurida, F., Nihayah, D. M., Kistanti, N. R., Setyadharma, A., & Novanda, A. (2021). City Branding Implementation as an Effort of Increasing Tourism Performance. *Review of International Geographical Education Online*, 11(3), 536-546.

13. Gössling, S., Scott, D., & Hall, C. M. (2020). Pandemics, tourism and global change: a rapid assessment of COVID-19. *Journal of sustainable tourism*, 29(1), 1-20.
14. Kasapi, I., & Cela, A. (2017). Destination branding: A review of the city branding literature. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(4), 129.
15. Latif, W. B., Islam, M. A., Noor, I. M., Mohamad, M., & Kongsompong, K. (2016). Imagination of brand image for tourism industry. *Problems and perspectives in management*, (14, Iss. 2 (contin. 1)), 138-142.
16. Mikáčová, L., & Gavlakova, P. (2014). The role of public relations in branding. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 110, 832-840.
17. Noori, A., & Nisa, S. (2019). An investigation on how brand image influences tourist destination and customer satisfaction: A case of the tourism sector. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 8(11), 3553-3559.
18. Santoso, R. (2022). Disrupsi Pandemi dan Strategi Pemulihan Industri Kreatif. *JMK (Jurnal Manajemen dan Kewirausahaan)*, 7(1), 48-58.
19. Scammell, M. (2015). Politics and image: the conceptual value of branding. *Journal of political marketing*, 14(1-2), 7-18.
20. Sekda Kota Sukabumi (2021). Wali Kota Sukabumi Presentasikan Potensi Ekraf ke Menparekraf Sandiaga Uno. Internet: <https://kdp.sukabumikota.go.id/2021/11/wali-kota-sukabumi-presentasikan.html>
21. Turan, C. P. (2021). What's inside matters: The impact of ingredient branding on consumers' purchasing behaviours in services. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 63, 102690.
22. UNWTO. (2022). International Tourism Consolidates Strong Recovery Amidst Growing Challenges, Internet: <https://www.unwto.org/taxonomy/term/347>
23. Utami, B. A., & Kafabih, A. (2021). Sektor pariwisata Indonesia di tengah pandemi COVID 19. *JDEP (Jurnal Dinamika Ekonomi Pembangunan)*, 4(1), 8-14.

Cite this Article: Rahanandra Hadyan Anshari, Nila Armelia Windasari (2022). The Impact of Destination Image for Creative-Hub Business: Case Study of Bumi Arsa Creative Space. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(12), 4929-4941